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Fatigue and Damage Mechanics of Composites

Progressive Damage Behavior of Plain-woven CFRP under Tensile-tensile Cyclic Loading

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Introduction

Woven composites ··· Widely applied as aerospace components

- ❑ Higher resistance for impact from out-of-plane direction
- ❑ Better formability and easily applied for curved geometry

Challenges

- ❑ Prediction of **damage propagation behavior under cyclic loading**
- ❑ Precise evaluation of **residual life**

Micrograph of plain-woven CFRP

- ✓ **More complex fatigue properties**
(fiber/resin types, fiber orientation etc. + **woven structure types**)
- ✓ Macroscopic damage modes **interacting with each other**
(fiber fracture, transverse crack, delamination etc.)

Introduction

Existing research

- Focusing on **stiffness degradation** during fatigue test
- Not focusing on **damage propagation** in detail

Typical failure of shear coupon*1

Stiffness degradation against fatigue cycle*1

Accurate prediction of damage behavior under fatigue loading leads to **improvement of long-term reliability.**

Goal

Evaluate fatigue damage propagation of plain-woven CFRP

*1: S. Wicaksono, G. B. Chai : Compos. Struct., 119 (2015), 185-194

Tensile-tensile fatigue test

Objectives

- ✓ Obtain $S-N$ relationship
- ✓ Observe final fracture mode

Specimen(VaRTM method)

- ✓ T300-3K-40A plain-woven cloth 4plies
- ✓ Epoxy resin impregnated

Specimen(Prepreg)

- ✓ W-3101/Q-1120E plain-woven prepreg 4plies

Conditions

- ✓ Test machine : Instron E20000
- ✓ Stress level $S = 0.9, 0.85, 0.8, 0.7, 0.6, 0.5$
- ✓ Stress ratio $R = 0.1$
- ✓ Frequency : 10 Hz

VaRTM method.

VaRTM specimen.

Prepreg specimen.

Results (VaRTM specimen)

Low cycle fatigue (LCF) mode
(2×10^4 cycles, $S = 0.8$)

High cycle fatigue (HCF) mode
(1.8×10^5 cycles, $S = 0.8$)

- ✓ High variability in $S = 0.8, 0.7$
- ✓ Two different damage modes appeared in the same stress level.

Edge surface of specimens were observed to evaluate damage modes.

Results (VaRTM specimen)

Edge surface observation

Low-cycle fatigue (LCF) mode (2×10^4 cycles, $S = 0.8$)

Transverse cracks and interface debonding were observed but not propagated largely.

Results (VaRTM specimen)

Edge surface observation

High cycle fatigue (HCF) mode (1×10^6 cycles, $S = 0.5$)

- ✓ More **transverse cracks** than **LCF mode**
- ✓ **Interface debonding** propagates and connects other interface debonding or **matrix cracks**. ⇒ **Wide range damages** in specimen

Results (Prepreg specimen)

$S - N$ relationship

- ✓ Large variation was observed in $S = 0.9$
- ✓ Different crack growth at the same stress level

Regardless of the specimen preparation method,
two different damage modes were observed.

HCF mode specimen

Damage observation by replica method^{*1}

Fatigue test interrupted at observation cycle and surface of specimen is transferred to film

⇒ **Fatigue damage behavior can be evaluated by microscope observation of film.**

Objective

Evaluating the difference of damage propagation between **LCF mode** and **HCF mode**

Conditions

- ✓ Test machine : Instron E20000
- ✓ Stress level $S = 0.6, 0.75$
- ✓ Stress ratio $R = 0.1$
- ✓ Frequency : 10 Hz
- ✓ Observation cycle : $1 \times 10^m, 2.5 \times 10^n,$
 $5.0 \times 10^n, 7.5 \times 10^n$ ($m = 1 - 6, n = 3, 4, 5$)

Replica method

*1: Kiyofumi SUZUKI, Manabu TAKAHASHI, Journal of the Japan Society of Engineering Geology 35 (1994), 77-78

Observation of edge surface of specimen

Edge surface transferred by replica film

Warps : Surrounded by black lines Wefts : Surrounded by white lines

Matrix : The other areas **Damages : Highlighted by red lines**

Results and discussion

LCF mode, 1.0×10^3 cycles

- ① Transverse crack in weft at **outermost layer**
(Caused by fatigue loading and compression stress from out-of-plane direction)

This damage occurs in both HCF/LCF modes but **not evolve into interface debonding**.

Results and discussion

LCF mode, 1.0×10^3 cycles

② **Fiber bundles/matrix interface debonding when phase difference between 2plies is 180°**

✓ Vertical stress occur at the interface because of undulation of fiber bundles.

Results and discussion

HCF mode, 7.5×10^4 cycles

- ② Fiber bundles/matrix interface debonding **when phase difference between 2plies is 180°**

This damage also occurred in both **HCF/LCF mode**.

Results and discussion

HCF mode, 5.0×10^5 cycles

③ Interface debonding advanced to **another interface via matrix cracks**, resulting in a longitudinal crack. (HCF mode)

Results and discussion

LCF mode, 2.5×10^3 cycles

Interface debonding occurred locally but were **not united each other**, resulting in early warp fracture.

Results and discussion

Edge surface observed by optical microscope (LCF mode, 3093 cycle)

Interface debonding evolved into transverse crack in weft and stress concentration occurred in warp.

Different damage propagation were observed between LCF and HCF.

Conclusion

Fatigue damage behavior of plain-woven CFRP was evaluated.

Summary

- Tensile-tensile fatigue test of plain-woven CFRP was carried out and **two fatigue modes** appeared.
- Damage observation by replica method showed that **transverse crack in weft** first occurred at **outermost layer**, regardless of the two fatigue modes.
- In **LCF mode**, interface debonding and transverse cracks occurred locally and did not propagate largely.
- In **HCF mode**, interface debonding were observed at wider range and connected each other.

Different damage propagation were observed between LCF mode and HCF mode.

Future works

- Investigating the reason why two fracture modes appears
- Numerically simulating fatigue damage modes

Appendix

Static tensile test

Objective

- ✓ Determine stress of fatigue test
⇒ Obtain static tensile strength

Specimen

- ✓ T300-3K-40A plain-woven cloth 4 plies
- ✓ Epoxy resin impregnated by VaRTM method
- ✓ Dimension : 150 mm × 15 mm × 1.4 mm

Stress-strain curve

VaRTM method

Plain-woven CFRP specimen

Obtained parameters

$$E_L = 40.5 \text{ GPa} \quad \sigma_u = 491.3 \text{ MPa}$$

Effect of the Crimp Gap between Fiber Yarns^{*1}

Phase difference of fiber bundles occurred in cloth stacking process can affect tensile properties of plain-woven CFRP.

High variability of fatigue lives of **LCF mode** may be due to **different process of stress concentration in warp and energy release** by cracks caused by crimp gap.

*1: Junji NODA, Masatoshi SEKI, Materials System, 34(2016), 21-28

Investigation by obtaining energy release rate

Crack direction is determined by required energy of crack propagation.

⇒ **Propagation condition based on energy release rate should be simulated.**

Energy release rate distribution in analysis model is obtained by **virtual crack closure technic (VCCT)**, and the results are compared with real crack propagation.

Multiple analysis models should be prepared considering phase difference.

RUC considering phase difference

No phase difference

Phase difference 90°

RUC considering phase difference

Phase difference 180°

Penetration between two plies

RUC considering phase difference

Compression stress from out-of-plane direction was enforced before the VCCT analysis for expressing penetration and deformed cross-section shape.

Conditions

- Enforce -10MPa to top shell
- Bottom solid : Discrete rigid, fixed movement and rotation
- Impose periodic boundary conditions to edge surface of the model

RUC considering phase difference

No phase difference

- Fiber bundles are deformed kidney shape.
- Deviation between up and down bundles and penetration occurred.

RUC considering phase difference

Phase difference 180°

Edge surface after the analysis

- Fiber bundles are deformed kidney shape.
- Deviation between up and down bundles and penetration occurred.

Edge surface observation

Static test specimen

- ✓ Transverse crack in weft and interface debonding were observed locally.
⇒ **Similar to LCF mode**

Summary of fatigue test

Two fatigue damage modes appeared.

① LCF mode

✓ No prominent interface debonding till final fracture

② HCF mode

✓ Interface debonding propagated into large area

Hypothesis

Final fracture of the specimen is suppressed
by propagation of interface debonding.

Damage accumulation should be observed.

Replica method

- ① Cover the jig for protecting acetone (Organic solvent)
- ② Drip acetone into the specimen
- ③ Stick replica film onto the specimen
- ④ Wait till end-face geometry of the specimen is transcribed to the film
- ⑤ Observe the film by optical microscope

Replica method for prepreg specimen

Surface of the specimen peeled off. (**Red highlighted zone**)
⇒ **Edge surface of the specimen was not able to be transferred accurately.** (Upper image)

Damage observation of prepreg specimen using replica method is difficult.

End face of the specimen after the test

VaRTM specimen after the test

LCF mode (20000 cycles, $S = 0.8$)

- ✓ Fiber fracture of warp bundle is dominant of final failure

VaRTM specimen after the test

HCF mode (180000 cycle, $S = 0.8$)

- ✓ **Interface debonding** were propagated specimen longitudinal direction.
- ✓ **Splitting** was also observed.

How to calculate V_f

- ① Measure the mass of the substrate before resin impregnation
⇒ Calculate the volume from its specific gravity
Before impregnation : 40.3 g ⇒ 22.90 cm³
- ② Measure the mass after VaRTM
⇒ Subtract the mass of the substrate to determine the resin volume
After impregnation : 91.8 g ⇒ 48.59 cm³
- ③ Calculate V_f from (fiber volume / total volume)

※ T300 : 1.76 g/cm³, Resin : 1.06 g/cm³

$$V_f = 32 \%$$

VaRTM

End-face observation

Static test specimen

Near to the failure point

- ✓ No damage was observed near to the failure point.
- ✓ Transverse crack in weft and interface debonding were observed locally.

Observation results

Area ① 1000cycle

Observation results

Area ① 100000cycle

Observation results

Area ① 250000cycle

Observation results

Area ② 7500cycle

Transverse crack was found at 2500 cycle.

Observation results

Area ② 75000cycle

Observation results

Area ② 500000cycle

Each cracks are united.
⇒ Crack is propagated into longitudinal direction.

Observation results

Area ② 1000000cycle

Interface debonding starts being **united and propagated into specimen longitudinal direction** in 100,000~500,000 cycle.

Results (HCF mode, $S = 0.6$)

7.5×10^3 cycle

Results (HCF mode, $S = 0.6$)

7.5×10^3 cycle

First transverse crack : 2.5×10^3 cycle (weft at **outermost layer**)

First interface debonding : 7.5×10^3 cycle

Results (HCF mode, $S = 0.6$)

7.5×10^4 cycle

Transverse cracks and interface debonding increased gradually.

Results (HCF mode, $S = 0.6$)

5.0×10^5 cycle

Interface debonding were connected and long crack along specimen longitudinal direction were formed.

Results (HCF mode, $S = 0.6$)

1.0×10^6 cycle

Interface debonding were connected each other from 1×10^5 to 5×10^5 cycle
 \Rightarrow Long crack along the specimen longitudinal direction was formed.

Results (LCF mode, $S = 0.75$)

1.0×10^3 cycle

Results (LCF mode, $S = 0.75$)

1.0×10^3 cycle

First transverse crack : 10 cycle (weft at **outermost layer**)

First interface debonding : 1.0×10^3 cycle

Results (LCF mode, $S = 0.75$)

2.5×10^3 cycle

Final failure : 3093 cycle

Interface debonding occurred locally but were not connected each other.

Different damage propagation were observed between LCF mode and HCF mode.